

Questionnaire to understand the socio-economic Status of Hadagali Jasmine Growers.

Greetings!

We are Ph.D. scholars at the Department of Commerce, MAHE, Manipal. Your valuable input is crucial for our socio-economic study, which aims to explore and understand the diverse aspects of our community's well-being. Your honest responses will contribute significantly to shaping policies and initiatives that address the needs and concerns of our community members. By participating, you are helping us gain insights into areas such as income distribution, employment patterns, educational attainment, housing, and other aspects that influence the overall quality of life. We want to assure you that all the information you provide will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Your responses will be aggregated and anonymized to ensure that individual identities remain protected. Your privacy is our priority.

(1) Age:

- a) Up to 30 years
- b) 31 – 40 years
- c) 41 – 50 year
- d) 51 – 60 years
- e) 61 years and above

(2) Gender:

- a) Male
- b) Female

(3) Educational Qualification:

- a) Illiterate
- b) Primary
- c) Xth
- d) + 2 and above

(4) Marital Status:

- a) Unmarried
- b) Married
- c) Divorced

(4) Family Style:

- a) Nuclear
- b) Joint family

(5) Number of Members in your Family

- a) Up to 2
- b) 3 – 5
- c) 6 – 8
- d) 9 and above

(6) Nature of Involvement in Agriculture

- a) Heredity
- b) First-generation farmer

(7) Nature of Land ownership.

- a) Own land only
- b) Lease land only
- c) Both

(8) Area Irrigated (In Acres)

- a) Up to 1
- b) 1.1 – 2
- c) 2.1 – 3
- d) 3.1 and above

(9) Types of farming adopted

- a) Mixed
- b) Single

(10) Reason for Avoiding Mixed Cropping Pattern

- a) More disease
- b) Quality affected
- c) Yield affected
- d) All the effects

(11) Do you use any agricultural equipment?

- a) Yes
- b) No

(12) If yes, which type of agricultural equipment do you use?

- a) Tractor b) Cutter c) Weeder d) Sprayer e) Others

(13) Experience in jasmine cultivation

- a) Up to 10 years b) 11 – 20 years c) 21 – 30 years
b) 31 – 40 years e) 41 years & above

(14) Area under jasmine cultivation (in acre)

- a) Up to 1 b) 1.1 - 2
c) 2.1 – 3 d) 3.1 and above

(15) What is the average life of jasmine plant?

- a) Up to 5 years b) 6 – 10 years
c) 11 – 15 years d) 16 years and above

(16) What factors influenced you to cultivate the jasmine?

(Rank as per your order of priority)

- a. Suitability of soil
b. Availability of water
c. More returns
d. Less risk

(17) Could you please quote the quantity of jasmine produced by you?
(Averagely per acre in kilograms) in a Year.

In peak season -

In lean season -

(18) Sources of irrigation

- a) Wells
b) Bore wells
c) Wells and Bore wells

(19) What is the nature of existing water facility?

- a) Sufficient
b) Moderate
c) Insufficient

(20) Your opinion on existing labour

- a) Insufficient
b) Sufficient

(21) Do you need permanent labour?

- a) Yes
b) No

(22) Would you be able to get the required labourers for jasmine cultivation?

- a) Yes b) No

(23) If No, what alternatives are arranged by you?

(24) If yes, nature of work assigned to permanent labour

- a) Jasmine-related works
b) Other crop works
c) Family works

(25) Do you give advance money to the labour?

- a) Yes
b) No

(26) Opinion on wage

- a) High wage rate
- b) Normal wage rate
- c) Low wage rate

(28) What is the source of finance?

- a) Own fund
- b) Borrowed funds
- c) Both

(30) How do you sell the flowers? (To whom sold)

- a) To pre-harvest contractors
- b) Direct to consumer
- c) Direct to the retailer through commission agent
- d) Direct to wholesaler/commission agent

(32) What is the average annual net income per acre

- a) below Rs.5,000
- b) Rs.5000-10000
- c) 10000-15000

(34) Who owns the flower market/ centre / place ?

- a) Private Party
- b) Municipality
- c) Association

(36) Value addition undertaken by the farmer for Hadagali Jasmine?

- a) Garland making
- b) Colouring the flower
- c) Reaching the untouched market
- d) Others _____

(37) On an average the cost incurred for the transportation of Hadagali Jasmine per kg?

- a) 0-20
- b) 20-40
- c) 40-60
- d) 60-80
- e) 80 and above

(38) How are the plucked Hadagali Jasmine are transported

- Own vehicle
- Taxi cars
- Trucks
- Bus
- Other _____

(27) Mode of transport up to the market:

- a) by Bus
- b) by Cycle
- c) by Lorry / Van
- d) Train

(29) Sources of borrowings

- a) Commission agents
- b) Moneylenders
- c) Commercial banks

(31) Commission charges:

- a) per kg. (Rs):
- b) per bud (Rs):

(33) Do you have flower growers' associations?

- a) Yes
- b) No

(35) How the Hadagali Jasmines are packed

- a) Gunny bag
- b) Plastic bag
- c) Bamboo basket
- d) Leaves of different plants

(39) What is the yield (kg) harvested in an acre?

- a) Less than 10
- b) 10-30
- c) 30-60
- d) more than 60

(40) Average price received for the jasmine grown per Kg

- a) less than 50
- b) 50-100
- c) 150- 200
- d) 250 and above

41) How does the middle man help in the selling of the jasmine flowers?

- a) For transporting
- b) Purchasing the flower
- c) Dealer for the flowers
- d) Other _____

42) How far is the market where the jasmine is sold?

- a) 1-20km
- b) 20-40km
- c) 40-60km
- d) 60 and above

43) Do you try to increase the life span of the jasmine flower grown?

- a) Yes
- b) No

44) Do you use refrigerator for increase the self-life of jasmine?

- Yes
- No